

Resveratrol: An incredible Naturaceutical with numerous Health Benefits

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Abstract

Nowadays, due to rising incidence of both communicable and non-communicable diseases, efforts to discover novel and effective disease-protective agents have led to the identification of plant-derived lead molecules such as resveratrol. Plants containing resveratrol have been used efficiently in traditional medicine for over 2000 years. It is commonly found in grapes, apples, blue berries, plums, peanuts and red wine. Therefore, it can be administered by either consuming these natural products or by taking nutraceutical pills. Resveratrol exhibits a wide range of beneficial and pharmacological properties, and this may be attributed to its molecular structure, which endows resveratrol with the ability to bind to several biomolecules. Resveratrol play critical roles in human health and is well known for its diverse biological activities such as antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer anti-diabetic and antimicrobial properties. Several *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies have evidenced the therapeutic efficacy of resveratrol in various diseases such as diabetes mellitus, cancer, cardiovascular disease, metabolic syndrome, obesity, inflammatory, neurodegenerative and several age-related diseases. Resveratrol significantly improves blood glucose control and insulin sensitivity in individuals with diabetes but does not affect glycemic measures in non-diabetic persons. This review presents an overview of currently available studies on the preventive and therapeutic properties and essential molecular mechanisms involved in the role of resveratrol in the prevention and treatment of various diseases.

Keywords: Resveratrol, Pharmacological properties, antioxidants, Diabetes mellitus, Anticancer.

Introduction

It is a general belief that it is easier to prevent a disease than to cure it. Advances in various branches of science provide evidence that the phytochemicals derived from the plants are capable of modulating the genes and cell functions. Phytochemicals are ecologically derived secondary metabolites synthesized by the plants to protect themselves from the environmental factors such as extreme cold, high temperature, UV radiation, and microbial invasion [1-3]. Amazingly, these secondary metabolites elicit beneficial as well as therapeutic actions against several human ailments [4]. Compared to humans, plants have highly developed protective systems because of their sessile nature and hence they serve as a rich source of novel substances for therapeutic applications. In fact, almost 70% of all drugs currently approved by FDA and widely prescribed to treat human primary and secondary ailments have been originally identified from natural sources and their demand is increasing exponentially because of the growing recognition of natural products as being non-toxic, more efficacious, available, accessible and affordable [5,6].

Our ancestors recommended distillations, combinations, reproductions or variations of substances that are originally derived from the plants to cure several dreadful diseases, long before their medicinal values are established scientifically and their golden words are fulfilled by current scientific accomplishments [7]. Using natural products as an essential means for the development of new pharmaceutical leads is continuously expanding and is a research field of substantial interest because the different structural range of natural compounds can provide novel lead molecules for therapeutic application based on rationalized molecular modifications. Modern medicine is often referred to as “evidence-based medicine” which ensures the safety of the herbal or natural products, standardization and development of processing aspects for successful therapeutic purposes [6,8].

Resveratrol (RSV) is one such phytochemical which lacks methodical scientific scrutiny for most of its therapeutic applications. Chemically resveratrol is *trans* 3, 5, 4'-trihydroxystilbene with a molecular formula $C_{14}H_{12}O_3$ and molecular weight of 228.24 g/mol. It is an off-white powder with a melting point of 253 to 255°C [9-11]. Its stilbene structure is related to the synthetic estrogen diethylstilbestrol. The essential structural skeleton of the molecule comprises two aromatic rings linked by a styrene double bond, which facilitates *trans* and *cis* isomeric forms of resveratrol [12]. *Trans*-resveratrol is relatively stable, if protected from light and high pH buffers, and has been shown to be the more biologically active form of resveratrol. Apart from the stereochemistry of the styrene bond, the positions of the phenolic substitutions on the aromatic rings of resveratrol play a significant role in determining its biological activity [13,14].

RSV is a phenolic micronutrient that is formed naturally by 70 different plant species, such as grapes, berries, peanuts, and pines [15-17]. It was first identified in 1940 from the white *hellobore lily* *Veratrum grandiflorum* O.Loes. [18-20]. The synthesis of *trans*-resveratrol in plants can be induced by microbial infections, ultraviolet radiation and exposure to ozone. The occurrence of resveratrol was popularized in 1992 when it was discovered as indispensable constituent of red wine, and implicated in the “French Paradox,” an epidemiological finding of an inverse relationship between red wine consumption and the incidence of heart diseases [21-23]. Red wine approximately contains 6.5mg/liter of resveratrol [24-26]. Although resveratrol is a naturally occurring polyphenol that has been isolated from several plant species, it is not feasible to isolate this compound in sufficient amounts required for extensive biological studies. It has been reported that 1 kg of dried grape skin can yield only 92 mg of resveratrol.

[27]Walle *et al.*, 2004 studied the absorption, bioavailability and metabolism of ^{14}C -resveratrol after oral and intravenous doses of administration in human volunteers and found that at least of 75% was absorbed with a peak plasma concentration of about 2 μ M and a plasma half-life of 9.2 \pm 0.6 hours. Despite 70% absorption of resveratrol in the body, studies performed on experimental rats showed that its bioavailability is relatively low because of its rapid metabolism in the liver and intestine [28-

30]. Resveratrol bioavailability exhibits variability from one individual to another that depends on age and gender [31, 32, 11, 33]. Chen *et al.*, (2024); reported that resveratrol metabolism by human gut micro biota shows distinct inter individual diversity based on the study of health-related effects of this compound [34]. Several resveratrol-derived metabolites also have been reported in the plasma and urine of animals and humans [35-37]. Studies performed on animal models have shown no apparent adverse effects of resveratrol [38-40].

The overall aim of this research article is to reveal the prospective beneficial effects of resveratrol and its therapeutic mechanisms in alleviating various diseases. Nowadays, resveratrol attracts increasing attention due to naturally occurring compound with a wide range of biological activity and preventive effects on different diseases such as cancer [41-43] neurodegenerative diseases [44-46], cardiovascular disease [47-49] anti-inflammatory[50-52]and antioxidant activity[53-55]. Besides resveratrol, different oligomers [56-58] of this compound were found to exhibit pivotal biological activities, such as antiviral, anti-fungal, antibacterial, and anticancer activities [59-61].

It is a fact that the development of a typical drug involves 10 to 15 years of extensive testing involving as much as a billion dollars [62-64]. Several methods have been developed to detect the presence and measure the levels of resveratrol and its analogs based on the use of HPLC and Gas Chromatography. Although resveratrol is reported to have many biological properties and implications for human health and disease, given its low levels in food sources, including red wine, it is unlikely that desired biological endpoints will be achieved from normal dietary consumption. In addition, its bioavailability and concentration in blood and tissues may descend well below levels required for most biological activities. Resveratrol can either cross passively cell membranes or interact with membrane receptors. Therefore, it may interact with extracellular and intracellular molecules. For this reason, its mechanism of action at the cellular level may be triggered by either activating signaling pathways when binding to cell membrane receptors, activating intracellular mechanisms, or even developing its effects inside the nucleus[65-66]. The low bioavailability of resveratrol was encumbered by its therapeutic application. However, the inherent structural simplicity of the resveratrol molecule permits for the rational design of new chemotherapeutic lead molecules and therefore, modification of resveratrol structure has received special interest from researchers [67]. Several resveratrol derivatives have been synthesized, such as methoxylated, hydroxylated and halogenated derivatives, and all of them exhibiting constructive therapeutic efficacy [68-70]

Resveratrol is present in dietary products as glycosylated form, known as piceid. Though, human digestive tract possess enzymes capable of triggering polyphenol oxidation and subsequent inactivation, the glycosylation prevents enzymatic oxidation of resveratrol, thereby preserving its biological effects and increasing its overall stability as well as bioavailability[27,71,72]. Since intestinal cells can absorb only resveratrol aglycone form, absorption process requires glycosidases. Therefore, the relative aglycone and glycosylated resveratrol amounts in foods and beverages may modulate its absorption rate [73-75].

ANTIOXIDANT PROPERTIES

Numerous studies have evidenced that resveratrol is a potent antioxidant [76-78] that also exerts anti-inflammatory, anti-aggregate, and neuroprotective properties[79-81]. Resveratrol has become an attractive molecule as a therapeutic agent in the treatment of a variety of pathological conditions, including neuro degeneration, cancer, cardiovascular disease, and diabetes mellitus [82-84]. The mechanisms underlying the beneficial effects of resveratrol are chiefly related to its antioxidant activity that protects vital tissues, such as liver, brain, and kidney, against different damages caused by oxidative stress[79,85,86]. It has the potential to promote the activities of a variety of antioxidative enzymes. The efficacy of polyphenolic compounds, such as resveratrol, to act as antioxidants depends on the redox properties of their phenolic hydroxyl groups and the potential for electron delocalization across the chemical structure. The credit of resveratrol as a potential antioxidant was established by

three different mechanisms (a) competition with coenzyme Q and to decrease the oxidative chain complex, the site of ROS generation, (b) scavenging oxygen radicals formed in the mitochondria and (c) inhibition of lipid peroxidation induced by Fenton reaction products [87-89].

Atherosclerosis, a complex process between monocytes/macrophages, epithelial cells and muscle cells, is characterized by lipid accumulation in the arterial wall and initiates with the attraction, recruitment, and activation of different cell types which provokes a local inflammatory response. Several significant targets contribute to the development of atherosclerotic lesions. The major ones are low density lipoproteins (LDL) which are generated in the circulation by remodeling of very low density lipoproteins (VLDL) through the process of lipolysis and the exchange of lipids and proteins with high-density lipoproteins (HDL). During transit in the circulation, oxidative changes may occur, affecting the lipids [90-92]. Several reports are available in the literature to support the suggestion that resveratrol interferes with several antioxidant mechanisms leading to the inhibition of atherosclerosis[93-95]through its peroxy radical scavenging activity and inhibiting lipid peroxidation to reduce MDA content [96-98]. Other investigations have shown that resveratrol inhibits apoptotic neuron cell death induced by ox-LDLs through inhibition of nuclear factor kappa B (NF-Kb) and activator protein-1 pathways [99-101].Sun and Sun (2001) reported that resveratrol protected the brain from neuronal damage because of chronic ethanol administration and suggested that it might be used as a therapeutic agent to ameliorate neurodegenerative processes[102-104].

Resveratrol has also been established as a potent activator of the histone deacetylase Sirtuin1 (Sirt1) [105-107], the first identified mammalian homolog of yeast Sir2, which is activated in response to fasting and calorie restriction[108-110]. It has been extensively demonstrated that the beneficial effects of Sirt1 activation in life span extension[111-113]. Interestingly, other studies have revealed that activation of Sirt1 increases insulin sensitivity and protects against metabolic damage produced by a high-fat diet[105, 114,115].

ANTI-INFLAMMATORY PROPERTIES

Inflammation plays a pivotal role in the pathogenesis of a wide variety of diseases, including cardiovascular diseases, cancer, diabetes, Alzheimer's disease, and autoimmune diseases. Drugs that can suppress inflammation thus have a potential in mitigating the symptoms of the disease. Resveratrol elicits antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties and thus may have the potential in the treatment of these diseases. Microarray analysis has also shown that resveratrol differentially modulates the expression of many genes in multiple cell-signaling pathways[116-118]. Activation of cyclooxygenase (COX) -2 results in the secretion of prostaglandin E2, which causes inflammation. Most of the COX-2 specific inhibitors prescribed to treat pain, fever, arthritis and cancer elicit cardio toxic effect. Interestingly, resveratrol is a potent inhibitor of COX-2 [119-121]. Hydroxylated resveratrol analogs represent a novel class of potent inhibitors and promising candidates for *in vivo* studies.

ANTI-TUMOUR PROPERTIES

Tumors of diverse histological origin exhibit specific and common molecular markers involved in their initiation, progression and onset. Resveratrol has been reported to have affected several intracellular targets that are key regulators of cell cycle and cell survival or cell lysis. Resveratrol is known to counteract the altered functionality of proliferative versus apoptotic pathways, exerting an antitumor activity either as a cytostatic or as a cytotoxic agent that depends on cellular precise pattern of expression of proteins related to tumorigenesis. Antiproliferative effect of resveratrol have been reported to lead frequently to apoptotic cell death [122-124]. Resveratrol is also considered as a chemopreventive agent because of its ability to block the induction of phase I enzymes that transform pro-carcinogen to carcinogen [125-127]. Resveratrol was shown to induce p53 gene expression in prostate cancer cells [128, 129,126] as well as to induce its activation by serine phosphorylation via MAPK [130-132]. Cancers of the digestive tract, pancreatic, esophageal, gastric and colorectal carcinoma- have high

incidence and poor prognosis because of the lack of an effective chemotherapeutic approach. Resveratrol treatment has been shown to arrest proliferation and to induce apoptosis in esophageal [133-135] pancreatic [136-138] gastric [139-141] and colon [142-144] cancer cells. Lung cancer presents four main histological types of cells; adenocarcinoma, squamous or large cell carcinoma, non-small-cell lung cancer (NSCLC), and small-cell lung cancer (SCLC). Resveratrol has been proposed to block lung cancer initiation since it was shown to be a competitive inhibitor of AhR [145-147] and to inhibit receptor transcriptional activity, therefore preventing induction of phase I enzymes in human bronchial epithelial cells [148-150].

Skin cancer can originate as a multistep process mainly because of repeated ultraviolet exposure, from epithelial cells and pigment producing melanocytes. Keratinocytes developed in moderately or highly aggressive carcinomas and melanocytes may form dysplastic nevi and melanoma, a highly metastasizing tumor. Skin cancer is usually resistant to radiotherapy and chemotherapy. Basal cell carcinoma is often associated with a specific mutation in the proliferation pathway triggered by membrane receptors. The apoptotic response is linked to multiple alterations of oncogenes/ oncosuppressors aimed at impairing cell death and favoring cell survival [151-153]. Epidermoid carcinoma cells treated with resveratrol have shown to arrest their cell cycle. It has been shown to inhibit melanoma proliferation by blocking the cell cycle in S phase [154-156] Niles and co-workers 2003 reported that a melanotic cell line was more sensitive to resveratrol induced apoptosis than an amelanotic cell line and this was associated with an enhanced phosphorylation of ERKs (Extra Cellular Signal Regulated Kinases) in the sensitive cells only [157, 158].

Hepatocellular carcinoma is a deadly tumor. The etiology is often associated with chronic viral infections and alcohol abuse, but multiple concurring agents and genetic alteration often exist. Resveratrol has been reported to inhibit hepatocellular carcinoma cell line proliferation and to induce apoptosis [159-161]. Several studies showed that resveratrol administration at a concentration of approximately 10mg/kg b.w/day to experimental animals impairs growth of transplanted hepatoma [162-164]. Resveratrol treatment is known to enhance immune response by promoting macrophage cytotoxicity against the tumor progression [165-167].

Most of the brain related tumours arise in the central nervous system and develop from glial cells and more rarely from neuronal cells. Childhood tumors, commonly known as primitive neuroectodermal tumors, are more frequently medulloblastoma and neuroblastoma. Neuroblastoma develops at the embryonic stage and, in over 10% of cases, regresses spontaneously in patients under one year of age, by cellular differentiation or apoptosis. In the remaining cases, the tumor grows aggressively and there is no cure. Nervous system carcinogenesis is related to somatic genetic changes due to environmental exposure and to inherited mutations. Alteration patterns are extensively characterized and are tumor and tumor-stage specific [168-170]. Resveratrol has been reported to have cytotoxic effects in human medulloblastoma and neuroblastoma [171-173]. It impairs apoptosis in stress-stimulated neuronal cells [174-176]. Resveratrol was demonstrated to arrest the proliferation of several medulloblastoma cell lines and to induce apoptosis, concomitantly with an increased expression in caspase-3 and phase I enzyme CYP1A1, possibly involved in resveratrol metabolic activation [177-179]. Intraperitoneal administration of resveratrol at a dosage of 40 to 100 mg/kg b.w/day shown to increase the survival rate of experimental mice subcutaneously injected with neuroblastoma cells [180-182].

Most ovarian cancers are epithelial and are under the control of steroid hormones that regulate proliferation and differentiation. Anti-estrogenic compounds may regulate receptor expression and counteract estrogen-induced proliferation. Endometrial carcinoma may arise as a multistep process involving genetic changes. The low-stage of this tumor appears with high incidence. It is estrogen dependent confined to the uterus, moderately differentiated and associated with microsatellite instability, silencing of DNA mismatch repair enzyme [183-185]. In endometrial adenocarcinoma cells, resveratrol exhibited antagonistic effects by inhibiting estrogen-induced alkaline phosphatase activity and progesterone receptor expression [186-

188]. Haematological malignancies develop as complications in genetic disorders, chromosome instability, impairment of DNA repair and bone marrow failure may facilitate proliferation of aberrant clones. The abnormal growth of bone marrow precursors occurs in leukemia and it may suppress proliferation of other clones of blood cells. Lymphomas are tumors of the lymphatic systems involving lymphocytes from lymph nodes, spleen and thymus. Myeloma originates from plasma cells in bone marrow and it is associated with excessive production of a specific type of immunoglobulin [189-191]. A common paradigm, assessed in a variety of lymphocytic and non-lymphocytic leukemias, is that resveratrol induces growth arrest [192-194]. Some authors showed that a low dose of approximately 10-30 of resveratrol is sufficient to arrest proliferation and a high dose of around 50 to 100 μ mol is cytotoxic [195-197]. A few authors compared the efficacy of resveratrol on tumor cells versus normal peripheral blood lymphocytes reporting a stronger and more significant cytotoxicity on leukemia cells [198-200,167]

ANTI-MICROBIAL ACTIVITY

In their natural environment, plants are constantly encountered by recurrent potentially pathogenic microorganisms such as fungi, bacteria, and viruses. The factors determining the resistance of plants against these pathogens belong to a large cache of constitutive and inducible (active) defense mechanisms [201-203]. These defense mechanisms are not only activated upon infection by microorganisms, but are also induced by stressors such as induction with ultraviolet light, or by chemicals such as surfactants, antibiotics, plant regulators, or the salts of heavy metals, as well as elicitors released by the pathogens or products resulting from the activity of fungal-degrading enzymes on host cell walls [204-206]. Constitutive plant defenses include structural barriers such as waxes, cutin, suberin, lignin, phenolics, cellulose, callose and cell wall proteins, which are often rapidly reinforced upon the infection process. Active defense mechanisms include the oxidative burst, rapid and localized cell death, the synthesis of pathogenesis-related proteins, and accumulation of phytoalexins [201, 207-208]. Phytoalexins are low-molecular weight antimicrobial secondary metabolites of wide interest, as they have been shown to elicit biological activity against a wide range of plant and human pathogens [204,209,210]. Stilbene phytoalexins, from the *Vitaceae* and other plant families, have been the subject of intense study during the past decade, because these compounds are thought to have broad insinuation in human health [204,211,212]

Resveratrol is present in grape wine as a constitutive compound acting as a phytoalexin in the defense response of grape fruits resistance against specific phytopathogens [213-215]. *Chlamydia pneumonia* (CP), an intracellular gram-negative bacterium, is known as a leading cause of human acute respiratory tract infections worldwide, accounting for 5-10% of all cases of pneumonia [216-218]. However, while CP infection begins in the respiratory tract, the bacterium is dispersed systemically in the bloodstream within alveolar macrophages, leading to the development of chronic infection. In many investigations, chronic CP infections have also been implicated as a contributory factor in the development of atherosclerosis and subsequent development of coronary artery disease [219-221]. There is substantial evidence to show that CP is an etiological agent of atherosclerosis or significantly increases the development of atherosclerotic plaque and coronary heart disease [222-224]. Resveratrol has a wide range of biological activities, some of which may explain its protective effect on coronary heart disease [225-227]. Schriever *et al.*, 2003 have shown that resveratrol inhibits the growth of CP in vitro with a minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of 12.5 μ g/ml. They suggested that resveratrol may exert its beneficial effects on the development of progression of CHD through its anti-bacterial effect on CP [225,228,229].

Helicobacter pylorus (HP) is a curved or spiral-shaped bacteria positioned on the gastric epithelium of patients with chronic active gastritis. Its discovery as the main etiologic organism of chronic gastritis and peptic ulcer disease was one of the most momentous discoveries in gastroenterology of the twentieth century [230]. In 1994 *Helicobacter pylori* was classified as a group 1 carcinogen and a definite cause of gastric cancer in humans by the International Agency for Research

on Cancer[231]. *Helicobacter pylori* have also been epidemiologically linked to adenocarcinoma of the distal stomach, and other investigations have also found a positive association between HP infection and colorectal adenomas [232-234]. In 2000, Mahady and Pendland demonstrated that resveratrol inhibited the growth of HP *in vitro*. The MIC₅₀ and MIC₉₀ were 12.5 and 25 µg/ml [235] Tombola *et al.*, 2003 assessed the effect of resveratrol on the activity of Vacuolating cytotoxin (VacA), a major virulence factor of HP and causes cell vacuolation and tissue damage by forming anion-selective, urea-permeable channels in plasma and endosomal membranes. Resveratrol is shown to inhibit ions and urea and cell vacuolation by reducing VacA activity suggesting that resveratrol may be useful in the prevention or cure of HP-associated gastric diseases [236-238].

According to traditional European and Chinese medicine, *Vitis vinifera* was a popular therapy to treat various skin diseases [239-241]. Both Gram-positive bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus* and *streptococcus* group D and Gram-negative bacteria, such as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Neisseria gonorrhoea* and *Neisseriameningitides* cause a variety of skin conditions, including folliculitis, impetigo, furuncles (boils), and cellulites. Treatments that combine anti-microbial and anti-inflammatory actions are attractive for alleviating most of the skin diseases that vary in severity. Resveratrol has been investigated against bacteria known to be major etiologic agents of human skin infections. The growth of the bacterial species *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, and *P.genius* was inhibited by resveratrol in concentrations of 171-342 µg/ml [242-245]. Indeed, resveratrol has been shown to competently inhibit *Candida albicans* growth[246-248]. Dimethoxy resveratrol derivatives exhibited antifungal activity against *C. albicans* with minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values of 29–37 µg/mL, including against 11 other *Candida* species [249-251]. In another study, resveratrol antifungal activity against *C. albicans* could be reached at 400 µg/mL, minimizing the antifungal role of resveratrol against *C. albicans*-caused infections[252-254]. Resveratrol inhibited biofilm formation and promoted biofilm dispersion even at sub-MIC concentrations and therefore could be developed as a new anti-biofilm agent to enhance foods shelf-life and safety [255-257]. *Pseudorabies* virus is one of the devastating pathogen of swine for which there is no treatment and that often results in economic losses. Resveratrol showed antiviral activity by inhibiting the *Pseudorabies* virus replication and effectively increase the growth performance and reduce the mortality of *Pseudorabies* virus-infected piglets [258-260] .

Type 2 diabetes is the most common form of diabetes. About 90% of all diabetic patients have type 2 diabetes. In these patients, the body resists the effects of insulin hormone or shows an insulin secretion deficiency. It is well established that factors such as inflammation and oxidative stress contribute to aggravation of insulin resistance and to β-cell failure in type 2 diabetics [261-263] .Besides, insulin resistance in adipocytes, hepatocytes, and muscle cells is still obscures the issue. In this context, animal studies provided firm evidence that resveratrol, as a natural compound, has beneficial effects on both mechanisms in these tissues and pancreatic β-cells [264-266]. In Sadeghi *et al.*, 2017 study, the conceivable role of resveratrol in ameliorating palmitate induced inflammation in C2C12 skeletal muscle cells investigated. The results indicated that anti-inflammatory effects of resveratrol are more likely to be a Sirtuin-1 (SIRT-1)-independent mechanism in skeletal muscle cells[267-269]. The results of several studies confirmed the SIRT-1 and AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) as the main molecular target for resveratrol to protect against pancreatic β-cell dysfunction and improving insulin sensitivity [270-272]. Actually, activation of these targets by resveratrol as a drug led to cellular and enzymatic phenomena, including decreased lipid accumulation, inflammation, and oxidative damage in liver, muscle, and adipocyte tissues and ultimately led to insulin action improvement in type 2 diabetes. However, another mechanism suggested in different studies, including increased phosphorylation of insulin receptor, IRS-1 expression, and phosphorylation of Akt [273-276]. In another *in vivo* study performed by Cheng *et al.*, 2015, it has been shown that resveratrol promoted nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor-2 (Nrf2) phosphorylation, in the pancreas of methylglyoxal-treated mice. This finding supports that resveratrol may be useful in the treatment of type 2 diabetes by protecting against pancreatic cell dysfunction [277-279]. Oxidative stress is also another factor contributing to β-cell failure in type 2 diabetes, and according to animal investigations, resveratrol decreases the antioxidant damage of β- cells to improve insulin sensitivity in insulin resistance condition in different animal models.

Resveratrol has been proposed as an antidiabetic drug since it improves insulin secretion and sensitivity, reduces glucose levels, and protects against metabolic damage[7,280,281]. Some reports have evidenced that resveratrol treatment improved insulin sensitivity in type 2 diabetic patients[282,283]. In fact, a double-blind, placebo-controlled study showed that a low dose of resveratrol orally administered improved insulin resistance in patients with type 2 diabetes [282,284,285]. In the animal model of type 2 diabetes (db/db mice) with decreased pancreatic β -cell mass, resveratrol was found to improve islet function, reduce oxidative stress, and decrease islet destruction and degenerative changes[270, 286,287]. Resveratrol partially prevents β -cell failure and increases β -cell mass. The management of diabetes involves three main aspects: reduction in blood glucose, preservation of β cells, and, with type 2 diabetes, improvement of insulin action. For instance, in the liver, resveratrol is metabolized to piceatannol, which can be released into the bloodstream and can further give rise to piceatannol glucuronides or piceatannol sulfates that can return to the gut [288-290]. Interestingly, resveratrol can also cause an increase of its own metabolism by enhancing the activity of phase II hepatic detoxifying enzymes [291-293].

Earlier, we have reported the anti-diabetic potential of resveratrol in streptozotocin-nicotinamide induced experimental type 2 diabetes in [294]. We have also reported the effect of oral administration of resveratrol on attenuating the key enzyme activities of carbohydrate metabolism in experimental diabetic rats [295]. We have reported the ameliorative potential of resveratrol on proinflammatory cytokines; hyperglycemia mediated oxidative stress and pancreatic β cell dysfunction in experimental type 2 diabetes in rats[296-298]. We have reported the *in vitro* glucose uptake activity of resveratrol by up regulating the expressions of GLUT 4, PI3 Kinase and PPAR in L6 myotube [299]. Recently, we have synthesized a new metformin-resveratrol aldehyde ligand and evaluated its glucose uptake efficacy using rat L6 muscle cells lines[300]. More recently, we have reported the molecular docking studies on a newly synthesized resveratrol aldehyde ligand against type 2 diabetic target proteins[301,302].

Conclusion and Future Perspectives

Resveratrol possesses significant beneficial as well as pharmacological properties. Resveratrol, like other derivatives, is one of the most promising compounds in anti-inflammatory drug formulation. Its attractiveness, amendments to their structure/bioavailability/activity, must be increased. Also, it has been shown that resveratrol can mimic caloric restriction effects, exert anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects, and even influence many diseases initiation and progression through several mechanisms. While there is a wealth of *in vitro* and *in vivo* evidence that resveratrol could be a promising therapeutic agent, clinical trials must confirm its potential.

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